

1 **Kinase and phosphatase inhibition as a signal transduction-centric approach to adjunctive**
2 **chemotherapies for the treatment of gynecologic cancers: PTPN3.**

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7 Men and women differ in large part resulting from the presence or absence of gynecologic organs
8 including the ovaries, the uterus, the lining of which is known as the endometrium, and the entry to the
9 uterus (womb), the cervix (1), all of which are targets for development of malignancies (2-7); vulvar
10 cancer is less common (8). Cancer, or unrestricted cell division which develops into a tumor after
11 remaining unchecked, evades active cell death and cell cycle control mechanisms, sustaining its survival
12 through growth factor signals (9) which are transduced to the nucleus to activate and repress transcription
13 of genes (10, 11). These signals are transduced between the plasma membrane and the nucleus by the
14 action of kinases and phosphatases, enzymes that utilize conformational changes and a catalytic site to
15 translate a signal from the extracellular environment to a change in gene expression. Catalytic sites are
16 pharmacologically targetable, and small molecule targeting of the appropriate kinase or phosphatase target
17 will disrupt or block this transduction (12, 13). We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (14, 15) to
18 identify and validate kinase and phosphatase targets in gynecologic oncology, including cancer of the
19 cervix. Here we describe a differentially expressed, up-regulated, and catalytically available phosphatase
20 target in cervical cancer: PTPN3.

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27 **Keywords:** kinase, phosphatase, signal transduction, gynecologic oncology, therapeutic targets in cancer,
28 chemical biology, systems biology of human cancer.

1 We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the
2 transcriptome (RNA), the proteome (total collection of proteins in the cell) and epigenetic modification
3 (eg., CpG-DNA) of human cancer (16-20). This includes the primary tumor, the source of the
4 transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - cancer subtypes, like adeno and squamous forms of
5 non-small cell lung cancer, metastasis to distant sites, including the lymph nodes, the lungs, the liver, the
6 brain, and bones, and the circulating tumor stem cell, which emerges from the primary tumor, disseminates
7 through the body and establishes a novel entity in a separate organ (21-26).

8 Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and
9 therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome
10 differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), administered in combination with FDA approved
11 broad-spectrum chemotherapeutics like CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully
12 complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies (27, 28) to blindly identify disease-specific,
13 subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities, fully augmented by novel
14 immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe a phosphatase therapeutic target identified through
15 rigorous study of the cervical cancer transcriptome: a phosphatase target that is up-regulated and
16 catalytically available: PTPN3.

17 Results

18 **Figure 1:** PTPN3 is differentially expressed in cervical cancer.

19 I. Primary tumors of the cervix from humans with cervical cancer.

20 *n*=5 normal cervical tissue

21 *n*=5 primary tumors (cervix; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
203997_at	0.01832588	-2.8055338	-3.18798	-1.0103752	PTPN3	2216/22277	90.1

22 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal cervical tissue and in primary
23 tumors of humans with cervical cancer (14), we discovered differential expression of protein tyrosine
24 phosphatase, non-receptor type 3, encoded by *PTPN3* in cervical cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The
25 expression of PTPN3 changed more than 90% of the human cervical tumor transcriptome when
26 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22277 transcripts (“Rank”).
27 Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PTPN3 messenger RNA in cervical tumors,
28 demonstrating up-regulation of PTPN3 during transformation of the cervix.

Thus, we concluded from blind study of one patient cohort that differential and increased expression
of PTPN3 likely defined the transcriptional landscape of cervical cancer in humans.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy). Small
molecule inhibitors of PTPN3 phosphatase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be
tested for efficacy in patients with cervical cancer, with the goal of identifying the most effective
phosphatase inhibitors for management of gynecologic malignancies. An approach that combines kinase
and phosphatase targeting with a recently described multi-catalytic strategy that targets dNTP synthesis,

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replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, likely delivered in conjunction with standard chemotherapies and drug resistance pump inhibitors in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance and disease (29).

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Methods

We utilized GSE63678 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors from humans with cervical cancer, as compared to normal cervix (along with GSE67522 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).